

Memo

To: The Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

From: Diaspora Solidarity Ghana

cc: Alban Bagbin, Speaker of Parliament, Republic of Ghana

Date: 9/28/2021

Re: Memorandum To the Ghana Parliament on “The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021”.

We are most grateful for the opportunity to address our concerns with this bill to your office. Our organization Diaspora Solidarity Ghana has reviewed the bill proposed by the National Coalition for Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values and our concerns are stated below.

We realize some in our community believe members of the queer community engage in behaviors and hold beliefs that run counter to our prevailing culture. The purpose of this letter is not to convince your office and committee on whether the activities or beliefs of this community are appropriate within the context of Ghanaian values but if we need to make laws to bring the community into conformity.

One of our former Supreme Court Justices in the judgment on the New Patriotic Party vs. Inspector-General of Police [1993] 2 GLR 459 - 509¹ wrote :

Most of the restrictions on our liberty which after years of repression we have come to accept are inconsistent with democratic norms. Except in a time of war, or when a state of emergency has been declared, it cannot be right for any agency of the executive to suppress the free expression of any opinion, however unpopular that opinion may be. The believer in absolutism and the anarchist, those who support and those who are opposed to abortion, those who favour and those who oppose equal rights for women, yes, lesbians and homosexuals too-are all entitled to the free expression of their views,

¹ New Patriotic Party v Inspector-General of Police, Original jurisdiction, ILDC 2548 (GH 1993), [1993-94] 2 GLR 459 SC, 30th November 1993, Ghana; Supreme Court

and the right to assemble and demonstrate in support of those views and to propagate those views.” Justice Kweku Etrew Amua-Sekyi.

This suggests that a law such as this one whose main objective is to enforce conformity to some set “cultural norms” is highly controversial in many respects.

The proponents are saying the bill is to protect the LGBT community. This statement has been questioned by many in the queer community since they do not believe their input had been appropriately sought. The LBGT community knows best what they need most by way of protection. We would therefore like to state that if the bill’s proponents are genuinely seeking to protect the LGBT community, they would need to withdraw the current bill. The proponents can then start discussions with the community on what kind of bill will be needed to protect the community.

Duty to promote ‘proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values’

This provision seeks to enlist the help of all in authoritarian positions to support and promote the proposed bill. It appears the intent is to initiate a prescribed written code of sexual expression which runs counter to how a free society operates. Sexual expression among humans is a language that is best understood by the participants involved. The idea that an individual or group of persons can stipulate and codify the expression of sexual desires among consenting adults can only mean those involved in this activity either have ill intent or do not really understand that all-important human function. There is nothing legal about making us all watch each other and instruct each other on how we are supposed to act in sexual situations.

Prohibition against undermining proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values

The authors of this bill took a select group of individuals of a certain persuasion without publicly enlisting the help or opinion of the general public. Their claim that their bill will help protect Ghanaian sexual and family values is disingenuous. Culture is dynamic and subject to change; as such this process should have been broader and if it is to be considered representative must have been done openly, not in backroom consultations. The youth and many groups and organizations with more in-depth knowledge were not consulted in coming out with the provisions of this bill.

The requirement that undermining of this bill is a crime creates an untenable situation in which a bad law once established cannot be repealed. This is a breach of the democratic norms on which our nation is established. At no time in this country has a law been passed that sought to codify what we as a people believed as well as criminalize any activities that seek to change public opinion. The above provision extends beyond the powers of our parliament, judiciary, and the executive branch of our government.

Duty to report

This requirement to report will create a means for blackmail and extortion and puts an undue burden on our institutions not to mention the additional financial costs.

Prohibition of LGBTTTQQAIAP+ and related activities

The idea of creating laws on how individuals should relate to each other in their most private and intimate moments is an issue that affects everyone. This extension of our legal system into our intimate lives is government overreach and must not be supported by any reasonable

person, straight, gay, lesbian, trans, or otherwise. That just smacks of enshrining voyeuristic elements within the legal framework of our great nation and violates article 18 subsection 2 of the constitution: the right to privacy.

Procuration

This part of the bill has no added benefit since it will be addressed by rape and prostitution laws and there is no reason that an offense involving non-heterosexual acts should be punished any different from such acts performed in a heterosexual context.

Detention with intent to commit prohibited sexual activity

As said in the above case, any such action must be punished irrespective of the context. We worry that listing separate different levels of punishment in this context will be a potential message to those involved in such activities and put the lives of our women who are the usual victims of such acts in jeopardy. All such acts are punishable by our current laws, and we support any efforts made to uphold such laws broadly. There is no reason why the punishment should be different in this context.

Keeping a brothel for a prohibited sexual activity

This is already punishable by our laws. The current law as written does go further and could be used to punish managers and proprietors of hotels and rest houses and even landlords for activities by consenting adults in personal relationships. This provision seeks to punish any person within whose property or establishment such activities occur. If applied as written business people and landlords can be compelled to spy on the sex lives of their clients to protect themselves from legal and financial liability.

This is an ambiguous provision that appears to be only targeted to the LGBT community. The nature of this provision is discriminatory and invades the personal lives of those in the community, violating Section 5, Article 18(2) of the constitution: the right to privacy. Additionally, it will only serve to create a hostile environment for all involved in any manner or form within the queer community. We support any effort by the government to regulate prostitution but invasion into private relationships is a breach of the human rights of those involved.

Prohibition of gross indecency

The definitions of gross indecency as written in the bill is as follows; "For the purposes of this section "grossly indecent act" means (a) public show of amorous relations between or among persons of the same sex, (b) public show of amorous relations between or among persons where one or more of the persons have undergone gender or sex reassignment; or (c) intentional cross-dressing to portray that the person is of a gender different from the gender assigned at birth with intent to engage in an act prohibited under this Act."

What this bill calls gross indecency entails the lives of individuals. This does not in any way affect public order or cause injury to any other parties. This provision represents an invasion of our legal system into the personal lives of individuals and must be resisted in the interest of the public liberty of all Ghanaians. It also targets a category of persons who have undergone gender and sex reassignment surgery, making it illegal for the general population to love them, whether in heterosexual or same-sex relationships.

Void marriage

This provision is exceptionally broad, and once again as we see in the said bill attempts to limit what individuals can do in respect of their own lives. In our nation marriage ceremonies are performed under different jurisdictions and only some of these directly involve our legal system. There is no reason why our legal system should stipulate a specific punishment for those involved in a specific form of marriage ceremony even if our laws do not recognize such a ceremony.

Prohibition of propaganda or, promotion of and advocacy for activities prohibited under this Act

This whole provision of this Act is illegal and contravenes our constitution as stated in our introduction. This can be described as best as a 'gag rule' that can only help set up a tyrannical provision that can in no manner or form be challenged and, even if constitutional, be improved upon. Our parliament should be very careful and not allow it to be led by emotional arguments to set up this damaging provision using majority support as the reason for doing that. Ghanaian citizens are dynamic like any other citizenry and the opinions of the majority over any issue will change over time. This has historically been the case for major religions in Ghana such as Christianity which, until relatively recently was foreign and a stigmatized belief system. This provision attempts to legally force perspectives on this issue to be frozen in time, stunting conversations and scholarly work that address this and similar topics. Additionally, our members of parliament will need to understand that such rules applied to a minority tend to move and spread to other groups. Our elders say, "when your neighbor's hut catches fire you grab a bucket." Our members of parliament should see this broad provision as one hut of our Ghanaian community that is on fire. The question that we need to ask is if someone wants to attack our community where will they start, and who will be next? This bill is not about the LGBT community, it is about the freedom of all Ghanaians, and we expect our Parliament to stand strong on this, irrespective of what the majority opinion is. We expect our members of Parliament to show us they deserve to be our gatekeepers on this.

Disbandment of LGBTTTQQAAP+ group, society, association, club or organization & Prohibition of funding or sponsorship for prohibited activities

At present, groups, societies, associations, clubs, and organizations that provide services to sexual and gender minorities are not contravening existing laws. They provide vital health services such as STI prevention, contraception, health screenings, and psychosocial support. They also provide paralegal support and raise awareness for minoritized groups. Without them, the heightened stigma in the Ghanaian society directed to them would lead to negative health outcomes. As sexual and gender minorities do not exist in isolation from the rest of the society, these negative health outcomes would eventually affect everybody whether directly or indirectly.

Prohibition of adoption order for LGBTTTQQAAP+ persons & Prohibition of grant of fosterage for LGBTTTQQAAP+ persons.

This provision claims to protect and support children, and this is an ideal that we support. The idea being propagated by this provision however appears to suggest though that queer folk are intrinsically child molesters and abusers. This false premise will end up being used to close the doors of the adoption system to a group most likely to benefit the needs of children. A review of over 40 original studies shows that children in same-sex parent households fare just as well as children in opposite-sex parent households "over a wide array of well-being measures: academic performance, cognitive development, social development, psychological health, early

sexual activity, and substance abuse.”² Most studies in child development have shown that childhood neglect and poor parental attachment as important factors influencing children’s propensity to be violent. Making adoption by the **LGBTQQIAAP+** community illegal has the potential of subjecting more children to conditions that could engender and promote neglect. The whole provision is completely antithetical to the ideals it proposes to achieve. No same-sex couple can have a baby by accident. Babies in a same-sex parent household by definition are in the custody of people that want them versus opposite-sex households who may not have planned for them. Logically, babies have a minimal chance of facing neglect.

Protection of victims of prohibited sexual activities

This provision claims to protect victims of prohibited sexual activities under the act. Whilst this appears to be a good idea the only purpose it serves beyond what is already covered under our laws as it relates to rape, and child molestation is to create opportunities for extortion targeted at the queer community. The only purpose this provision will serve is to create an unhealthy environment of mistrust and fear. This provision provides no new protections since minors and individuals coerced into sexual activities of any kind are already protected under Chapter 5 (kidnapping) and chapter 6 (sexual offenses) of our criminal code. There are many such cases in our legal system that are already poorly addressed; the laser focus on these protections to ‘victims’ of ‘LGBT activities’ has the potential of taking well-needed resources from a part of our legal services that is already poorly applied. We hope our parliament will see and address the plight of many women and children who continue to suffer from rape and sexual abuse in our community irrespective of the sexual orientation of the perpetrators.

Access to medical help or treatment by accused & Flexible sentencing

We understand the need to provide evidence-based medical care for all Ghanaians. The idea that queer individuals require medical treatment to reverse their sexual orientation is outdated and is no longer the prevailing view in the contemporary medical literature. This provision seeks to pathologize and criminalize whole communities and require members of the community to pay for unproven treatments in a bid to reduce the punishment applied. Since the group currently proposing this bill is already running such a center based on the words of Mr. Moses Foh Amoaning, the executive secretary of the National Coalition for Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values (which the bill is named after). This raises ethical issues and the possibility of conflict of interests. The treatments proposed have not been independently evaluated by any medical body and have been judged effective and must not even be considered in any manner thereof in any legal proceedings. As stated in a review by the Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine (Alempijevic D et al, 2020)³, treatments directed at sexual orientation are considered by most in the medical field as ineffective, cruel, inhumane, degrading, and of doubtful clinical benefit. There is a reported increased risk of negative psychological conditions in adult gay men exposed to these “treatments”.

Prohibition of extrajudicial treatment

Anyone who believes that this provision of this bill can in any way protect people targeted based on their lives or perceived sexual orientation or gender identity and expression is either extremely naïve or does not know the Ghanaian community well. The whole bill has 20 or more

² Manning, Wendy D et al. “Child Well-Being in Same-Sex Parent Families: Review of Research Prepared for American Sociological Association Amicus Brief.” Population research and policy review vol. 33,4 (2014): 485-502. doi:10.1007/s11113-014-9329-6. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4091994/>

³ Alempijevic, Djordje, et al. "Statement on conversion therapy." Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine 72 (2020): 101930.

provisions that demonize and dehumanize LGBTTTQQAAP+ persons and the authors then throw in one provision which is already covered in our laws, which prohibit extrajudicial activities of all kinds. In our opinion, if anyone would like to protect our community they should seek to reach out and better understand our community. Laws have so far failed, adding a single provision in this bill that seeks to criminalize LGBTTTQQAAP+ communities (who are part of all communities whether in Ghana or the diaspora) is only a total reflection of the disingenuous nature of this whole charade.

On account of the many illegal provisions and the social and psychological risks, this bill poses to the queer folk and the Ghanaian community at large we proposed the bill be withdrawn. If the authors would like to make laws to protect the queer community and protect our young people from predatory behavior, we suggest a plan involving dialogue with the community to come up with such laws if they are needed.

Yours truly,

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